

If data is reused in the forest and no one is around to hear it, did it happen? A citation count investigation.

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Abstract

In this practice paper I will describe the process and results of tracking a citation from a data repository through the article publication process and trying to add a citation to one of our DOIs. I will also discuss some other confusing aspects related to citation counts as indicated in various systems. Although I discovered numerous problems with citations, they still seem to be one of the best ways to determine if a dataset has been downloaded and used (rather than accessed by a bot), especially with repositories that do not require people to login or provide an email to download a dataset. Nonetheless, the lack of transparency in some these systems and processes obscures how and where data is being used.

Introduction

In my role as the Data Workflows Specialist at the University of Michigan Library, I reviewed large datasets and code deposits and developed data management workflows for researchers. I also supported various aspects of our research data repository, Deep Blue Data¹, which is based on the Samvera Hyrax² platform. In this capacity, I worked with our developers to improve connections between our system and others in order to gather various metrics including Altmetrics³ and citation counts for our datasets.

Deep Blue Data is an open access, general institutional data repository that does not require users to log in before downloading a dataset. As such, it provides no means to follow up on downloads to verify their re-use. Capturing citation counts is the only option to understand how and where Deep Blue datasets are being reused.

One method of capturing and displaying citation counts, particularly at “point-of-need,” is to use the DataCite Data Metrics Badge⁴ shown in Figure 1. In early January 2021, we added Data Metrics Badge to our repository. A few weeks later, I checked some of our more popular datasets to see if they were showing any citations and discovered they were not. Indeed, none of our more than 400 datasets showed citations.

Figure 1 DataCite Data Metrics badge frontend with no indication of citations.

I investigated further by spot checking datasets and found that although there were articles related to these datasets, as indicated in our “Citations to Related Materials” field, researchers did not appear to be citing their datasets in the “References” section of their papers. In some cases, they mentioned their dataset, complete with DOI, in the abstract of the paper. In other cases, they only indicated the existence of the dataset in the “Data Availability” statement rather than citing the dataset in both the “Data Availability” section as well as the “References” section (Ball and Duke, 2015). I assumed these errant practices were the root cause of missing citations. After researching the issue, I determined they are only partially to blame. Figure 2 was my rough understanding of the Data Citation Pipeline and the major players in my investigation.

Figure 2 The Data Citation Pipeline.

¹ Deep Blue Data: <https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/data>

² Hyrax: <https://hyrax.samvera.org/>

³ Altmetric: <https://www.altmetric.com/>

⁴ DataCite Data Metrics Badge: <https://support.datacite.org/docs/displaying-usage-and-citations-in-your-repository>

Problem Investigation

My investigation into the “0” citation count began in earnest when a researcher who I had been encouraging to cite his data in the “References” section informed me that he had just submitted a paper with the data cited in this manner. This paper provided me with a “known” example to track. The next step entailed waiting several months until the publication process was complete to see if the citation was recognized or not.

In case the “normal” citation count process was not working, I tried using “Contribute Citations”⁵ to our DataCite DOIs as mentioned by Cousijn et al. in the section “Contributing data citations: data repositories” (2019) as well as the “Make Data Count”⁶ movement, reasoning that it would at least indicate whether articles and datasets were linked somehow. I followed the instructions using the DataCite API with a JSON payload indicating that the DataCite dataset DOI “IsCitedBy” (Starr & Gastl, 2011) an article DOI. See Figure 3 for an example of a JSON payload⁷.

```
{
  "data": {
    "attributes": {
      "relatedIdentifiers": [
        {
          "relationType": "IsCitedBy",
          "relatedIdentifier": "10.1029/2019JC015306",
          "relatedIdentifierType": "DOI"
        }
      ]
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 3 JSON payload indicating that dataset DOI 10.7302/dbfp-s644 "IsCitedBy" article DOI 10.1029/2019JC015306 submitted to DataCite via API.

I used the following Curl command (run from the Mac Terminal):

```
curl -v -X PUT -H "Content-Type: application/vnd.api+json" --
user[redacted user]:[redacted passwd] -d @doi_update.json
https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.7302/dbfp-s644
```

The first problem appeared at this point. After submitting the JSON payload via API, there were no citations listed in the “Citations” field in the DataCite API results⁸, as shown in Figure 4. In addition, there were no new citations displayed on the DataCite Search⁹ results page for DOI 10.7302/dbfp-s644 as shown in Figure 5.

⁵ Contribute Citations: <https://support.datacite.org/docs/contributing-data-citations>

⁶ Make Data Count: <https://makedatacount.org/data-citation/>

⁷ Updating DataCite DOI Metadata with JSON Payload: <https://support.datacite.org/docs/updating-metadata-with-the-rest-api>

⁸ DataCite API results: <https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.7302/dbfp-s644>

⁹ DataCite Search: <https://search.datacite.org/works?query=10.7302%2Fdbfp-s644>

Figure 4 Result of "IsCitedBy" payload in "references" not "citations."

Figure 5 DataCite Search results for DOI 10.7302/dbfp-s644.

Through further investigating, testing, and pestering the very kind DataCite Support staff, I discovered a bug in DataCite’s system: using “IsCitedBy” causes the new citation to end up in the “References” section of the DOI, not in the “Citations” section.

In attempt to get a citation to show up, I used different “payloads” and checked other repositories that use DataCite and indicate citation counts. When I noticed that Dryad’s DOIs in the DataCite API view were using “Cites” instead of “IsCitedBy”, I promptly modified my “payload” accordingly and it worked. A single citation count was indicated in the “Citations” section. DataCite Support eventually created a DataCite GitHub issue¹⁰ for this bug.

The final version of the original article I had been tracking was published¹¹ in early November 2021 with its reference section hyperlinked. This allowed me to see how the dataset citation was formatted and whether it would be recognized as an actual citation of the dataset with the DataCite Data Metrics Badge in the Deep Blue repository. Much to my amazement and chagrin however, the dataset citation went from displaying the DOI in the references list, as shown in Figure 6, to completely ignoring the DOI altogether in the “Markup” view in Crossref API results, as shown in Figure 7 as number “7”. It should be noted that this was how it looked in early November 2021.

Figure 6 Dataset citation fully hyperlinked in the article references list.

¹⁰ DataCite GitHub issue #1416: <https://github.com/datacite/datacite/issues/1416>

¹¹ Long-Term Earth-Moon Evolution With High-Level Orbit and Ocean Tide Models <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JE006875>

```

7:
  key: "e_1_2_11_9_1"
  volume-title: "Long-term Earth-Moon evolution with high-level orbit and ocean tide models [Data set]"
  author: "Arbic B. K."
  year: "2021"
8:
  key: "e_1_2_11_10_1"
  doi-asserted-by: "publisher"
  DOI: "10.1029/2007GL030845"

```

Figure 7 Markup view the dataset citation in the Crossref API results.

Interestingly, the Google Scholar link¹² (circled in Figure 5), resolves to the AGU/Wiley article itself in a circular manner, not to the dataset itself (see Figure 8). Rather than pointing to Google Scholar, it seems that AGU/Wiley could point to DataCite Commons¹³, (they have links to Crossref for other citations) or even Google Dataset Search¹⁴, (Figure 9).

Figure 8 Google Scholar links to article in AGU not the dataset itself.

Figure 9 Screen shot of Google Dataset Search results for dataset title “Long-term Earth-Moon evolution with high-level orbit and ocean tide models.”

¹² Link to Long-term Earth-Moon article in Google Scholar:

<https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&q=Arbic%2C+B.+K.%2C+%26+Schindelegger%2C+M.+%282021%29.+Long%2%80%90term+Earth%2%80%90Moon+evolution+with+high%2%80%90level+orbit+and+ocean+tide+models+%5BDataset%5D.+University+of+Michigan%2%80%93Deep+Blue+Data.+https%3A%2F%2Fdoi.org%2F10.7302%2FZCK4-0058>

¹³ DataCite Commons: <https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org/10.7302/zck4-0058>

¹⁴ Link to Long-term Earth-Moon dataset in Google Dataset Search:

<https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?query=%22Long-term%20Earth-Moon%20evolution%20with%20high-level%20orbit%20and%20ocean%20tide%20models%22&docid=L2cvMTFwdmgyMjEyZA%3D%3D>

Armed with information about how dataset citations appeared to be processed — at least as compared to article citations at Wiley, — I reached out to Shelley Stall, Senior Director of Data Leadership at AGU, to inquire about this second issue since its markup was very different from how article citations were handled. It turned out that AGU along with several other publishers were working a on fix for this very problem and planned to implement it later in November. Figure 10 shows the citation after the initial fix (FORCE11 Software Citation Journals Task Force, 2022).

```
<citation key="e_1_2_11_9_1">
<unstructured_citation>Arbic B. K. &Schindelegger M.(2021).Long-term Earth-Moon evolution with high-level orbit and ocean tide models[Dataset].University of Michigan-Deep Blue Data.https://doi.org/10.7302/ZCK4-0058</unstructured_citation>
</citation>
```

Figure 10 The dataset citation "markup" after the initial fix.

Unfortunately, the AGU/Wiley initial fix does not help DataCite to see this citation mention in the references as a citation to the dataset in DataCite Commons¹⁵ frontend (Figure 11).

Figure 11 DataCite Commons frontend with 0 citations indicated.

What I was seeing with our datasets is described in the “Problem Statement” below. Even though our researcher was including [Dataset] in his citation it was being missed, which meant Crossref was not including it in their Event Data¹⁶. Consequently, DataCite would not know there was a citation to be counting.

‘Problem Statement:

When the journal production process validates these citations, the machine actionable version of the citation is – in present practice – not always handled optimally, and the integrity of the machine-actionable citation may be damaged. In

¹⁵ DataCite Commons results for DOI 10.7302/zck4-0058:

<https://commons.datacite.org/doi.org/10.7302/zck4-0058>

¹⁶ Crossref Event Data: <https://www.crossref.org/services/event-data/>

such cases, the citation will not be able to give automated attribution and credit to the software or dataset authors, nor will it support links to the other persistent identifiers associated with the article.’ (FORCE11 Software Citation Journals Task Force, 2022)

Current state of Issues

Since my initial investigations last year, I am pleased to report there have been fixes and improvements made. However, I can only report back on the “IsCitedBy” fix because the publisher/Crossref metadata fix is not yet showing for the DOIs that I have been tracking.

IsCitedBy

Now that DataCite fixed the “IsCitedBy” bug, we can see the results of pushing the “IsCitedBy” payload as described in Figure 1. In the DataCite API view,¹⁷ “IsCitedBy” shows as the “relationType” (see Figure 12) in addition to appearing correctly in the “citations” section (see Figure 13).

```

7:
  relationType:      "IsCitedBy"
  relatedIdentifier: "https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015306"
  relatedIdentifierType: "DOI"

```

Figure 12 relationType "IsCitedBy" for DOI 10.7302/dbfp-s644.

```

relationships:
  client: {}
  provider: {}
  media: {}
  references: {}
citations:
  data:
    0:
      id: "10.1029/2019jc015306"
      type: "dois"

```

Figure 13 "IsCitedBy" DOI payload now showing correctly in “citations.”

Finally, “1 citation” appears in the DataCite Search results¹⁸ (Figure 14).

Repository of current meter archive data used in Luecke et al. 2020 Journal of Geophysical Research Oceans paper
 Dataset published via University of Michigan
 The locations ("locs") files in this directory contain indices pointing to the locations in the CMA superset datafiles that were used in the Luecke et al. 2020 comparison of HYCOM and MITgcm model output to CMA observations.
 1 citation No usage information was reported.
<https://doi.org/10.7302/dbfp-s644> Cite

Figure 14 DataCite Search results for 10.7302/dbfp-s644 now showing 1 citation.

The Data Metrics Badge in Deep Blue Data also shows “1” (Figure 15).

¹⁷ DataCite API view: <https://api.datacite.org/doi/10.7302/dbfp-s644>

¹⁸ DataCite Search results for DOI 10.7302/dbfp-s644:
<https://search.datacite.org/works?query=10.7302%2Fdbfp-s644>

Figure 15 Data Metrics Badge showing 1 citation.

Publisher Fix

The publisher/metadata fix has been released but is not yet showing in the DOIs that I have been tracking.

According to FORCE11 Software Citation Journals Task Force the “Data Citation with registered DOI” should now have these fields: @citation_type=data, unstructured, DOI (2022). The dataset citation in the “reference” section of the Crossref data should look something like the following citation:

```
@citation_type = data
Unstructured: "Arbic B. K. &Schindelegger M. (2021).Long-term Earth-Moon
evolution with high-level orbit and ocean tide
models[Dataset].University of Michigan-Deep Blue
Data.https://doi.org/10.7302/zck4-0058"
DOI: 10.7302/zck4-0058
```

With the DOI split out and the citation type indicated, Crossref can update Event Data which would then be read by DataCite and the reference should show in the “referenceType” section.

[Note to editors/reviewers: I will update this section when the fix is finally pushed all the way through to the aforementioned DOIs]

Other issues of note

In addition to the issue with publishers that I have described, there are issues with data citations in other parts of the pipeline. One problem is how repositories sharing the data are making the suggested citation available. Another is that reference managers do not make it easy to create or manage a data citation through to the other end of the pipeline with data aggregators, nor do they make it clear whether they are sharing data citation metadata correctly.

The Deep Blue Data repository provides a suggested citation via plain text in the metadata section of the deposit (see Figure 16). The suggested citation must be highlighted and selected with a pointing device and copied to the clipboard to be used. Deep Blue Data does not currently have integrations with reference managers, nor does it make the citation available in other formats such as Biblatex. From the publisher’s standpoint, having [Data set] or [Dataset] in the citation is critical for their process as it is or should be an immediate indicator that this is indeed a dataset and should be handled as such.

To Cite this Work:
 Arbic, B. K., Schindelegger, M. (2021). *Long-term Earth-Moon evolution with high-level orbit and ocean tide models* [Data set], University of Michigan - Deep Blue Data. <https://doi.org/10.7302/zck4-0058>

Figure 16 Suggested citation for dataset 10.7302/zck4-0058 in Deep Blue Data.

Reference Managers, how are they handling data citations?

With Zotero, for instance, the results can differ depending on how you use the tool. Per my exchange with Zotero support, the “Browser plug-in” option pulls metadata information from COinS¹⁹ (ContextObjects in Spans) first then “meta tags.” It does not use Schema.org however. Alternatively, using the Zotero desktop application and providing a DOI via the “Add Item(s) by Identifier” option, will cause the metadata to be pulled from DataCite. The example in shown in Figure 17 shows the results of entering 10.7302/ZCK4-0058. In this case, the dataset is imported as “Item Type: Document” because Zotero does not currently have a “Data” Item Type. Until Zotero changes this they implemented a temporary measure in the form of a field called “Extra” that indicates “Type: dataset” and “DOI: 10.7302/ZCK4-0058.”

Figure 17 Screen shot from Zotero desktop “Add item by Identifier.”

Using the Zotero plug-in for Microsoft Word to “Add/Edit Citation” results in a citation that includes the [Dataset] designation. For an example, see (Arbic & Schindelegger, 2021) in the “References” section of this paper. Because the metadata in DataCite differs slightly from the suggested citation in Deep Blue Data, the entry in the References section is not the same as the suggested citation which is also less than ideal (see Figure 16).

Mendeley does not handle datasets well at all. It has no option to add a dataset by entering a DOI nor does the system does not search DataCite. Mendeley does not have a “Dataset” Document Type either—a fact confirmed by Mendeley Support in this response via email: “You can add the dataset into your library first then cite it using the citation plugin. Since there’s no Dataset document type, you can try the Generic document type.”

Biblatex²⁰ has had an option for datasets using @dataset since at least 2019.

It should be noted that the researcher who submitted this dataset, Dr. Brian Arbic, uses Overleaf²¹, a LaTeX editor supporting Biblatex, when preparing his papers. This way he avoided using Zotero or Mendeley and their issues with “type.”

In my cursory examination of citation styles as options of Zotero export, only APA supports the use of [Dataset] which is pulled automatically from the “Extra” field. Using another style requires including [Dataset] to ensure it won’t be missed downstream.

The concern with some of these manual copy/paste data entry issues and data not being handled natively as a “type” is that the designation [Data set] or [Dataset] might be lost along with the DOI.

¹⁹ Using Zotero to Create Metadata: https://www.zotero.org/support/dev/exposing_metadata/coins

²⁰ Biblatex Documentation: <http://linorg.usp.br/CTAN/macros/latex/contrib/biblatex/doc/biblatex.pdf>

²¹ Overleaf LaTeX editor: <https://www.overleaf.com/>

Data Availability Statements

Although using “Data Availability” statements might suggest a possible solution, it does not solve the problem. Crossref does not currently check the “Data Availability” statement for dataset DOIs and my investigation indicates that information is not currently passed from the publisher (at least not in the case of AGU/Wiley) to Crossref.

For evidence of this issue, I tracked a dataset DOI, <https://doi.org/10.7302/fn7r-hq31> mentioned in a “Data Availability” statement²² but not in the “References” section in an article in *Nature* (Figure 18).

Data availability
https://doi.org/10.7302/fn7r-hq31
Code availability
https://doi.org/10.7302/fn7r-hq31

Figure 18 Data availability statement for article <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-022-06257-6>.

Unfortunately, there is no indication that data availability statements in the metadata are shared with Crossref²³.

Dataset Aggregators

Dataset aggregators are on the other end of the dataset publishing pipeline and have their own problems because they are highly dependent on other systems earlier in the pipeline. Interestingly but not surprisingly, the Google Dataset Search²⁴ appears to be using their massive computing power to mine Google Scholar for any mentions of dataset DOIs. For example, one of our more popular datasets from the perspective of download and hits is the RIGA dataset²⁵. According to Google Dataset Search, it has 50+ citations. The article that is listed as a “related resource” in our repository only mentions the dataset DOI in the “Abstract” part of the paper.

Clarivate - Data Citation Index²⁶ seems to be somewhat unreliable for citation counts. For instance, when using “Deep Blue Data” as a search term in “Data Source,” it returns 4,000+ entries, see Figure 19. This is far more than we have in our system (400+). Upon researching this discrepancy, I discovered most of the so-called “datasets” were actually articles in another repository “Deep Blue Documents.” In addition, there are some actual datasets that are showing “1” citation and, for at least some of these, that citation was in fact listed in the “References” section of the related article. Unfortunately, in this case it is not showing in DataCite and therefore is not actually showing in our system as a citation count. It is not clear how the Data Citation Index is getting these citation counts. Is it only indexing the references sections of articles or are they getting their numbers elsewhere?

²² Data Availability Statement: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00382-022-06257-6#data-availability>

²³ Crossref metadata: <https://api.crossref.org/v1/works/10.1007/s00382-022-06257-6>

²⁴ Google Dataset Search: <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/>

²⁵ RIGA Data: <https://datasetsearch.research.google.com/search?src=0&query=10.7302%2FZ23R0R29&docid=L2cvMTFzbXcyeTN3Nw%3D%3D>

²⁶ Clarivate Data Citation Index: <https://clarivate.com/webofsciencgroup/solutions/webofscience-data-citation-index/>

Figure 19 Deep Blue Data results in the Clarivate Data Citation Index

I have included an updated and slightly more complete Data Citation Pipeline to include additional data sources and metadata forms, including Reference Managers, JATS XML²⁷, and Aggregators.

Figure 20 Updated Data Citation Pipeline.

Conclusion

My exploration was extremely small in scope but the number of issues I encountered in such a small sample suggest these problems may discourage researchers from citing their data (van de Sandt et al., 2019). My research also reveals that those of us in the data repository field cannot assume these citation and reference processes are working effectively. We need to test, check, and provide feedback to publishers, DOI organizations, and other systems in the citation pipeline, see Figure 20, if we want these systems to perform as we think they should. In addition, pushing aggregation databases such as Data Citation Index to be more transparent about their sources for dataset citation counts would help provide a more accurate picture of dataset reuse. If researchers are getting accurate citation counts, they will be more likely to cite their datasets and create a positive feedback loop for these systems in the process.

*** It should be noted that the purity of my process and results were somewhat compromised in the middle of this investigation because the Deep Blue Data repository was a participant in the RADS²⁸ project. As a result, most datasets that were published before March 31, 2022 had their DOI metadata “relationType” metadata fields including “IsReferencedBy” updated via script. ***

²⁷ JATS XML: <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov/>

²⁸ RADS project blog: <https://metadatagamechangers.com/blog/2022/3/7/ivfirlw6naf7am3bvord8pldtuyqn4r>

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